

SOLAR TRACKING SYSTEM CONTROL

M. Ahmed¹, E. C. Anene², I. T. Balami³ and A. U. Babuje⁴.

^{1,2,3}Electrical and Electronics Engineering Programme, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria.

⁴Mechanical/Production Engineering Programme, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

The main focus of this paper was to propose control algorithm for efficient tracking of solar radiation for a field controlled DC servomotor positioned photovoltaic (PV) module. The Ziegler-Nichols, pole placement and linear quadratic regulator approaches were utilized for this study and the results were successfully simulated using MATLAB 2010a. The results showed that: the rise time of 0.9800 seconds, peak time of 1.3600 seconds, settling time of 2.0150 seconds and overshoot of 10.3% were obtained without controller, arise time of 0.3600 seconds, peak time of 0.6950 seconds, settling time of 1.9150 seconds and overshoot of 19.8 % were obtained using the Ziegler-Nichols method, arise time of 0.1950 seconds, peak time of 0.5000 seconds, settling time of 0.4000 seconds and overshoot of 00.0 % using the pole placement method, arise time of 0.5750 seconds, peak time of 0.7600 seconds, settling time of 1.0100 seconds and an overshoot of 04.1 % using the linear quadratic regulator method, which implies that the pole placement control method was the best for the system.

KEYWORDS: Photovoltaic Module, Tracking, Solar Radiation, Control Algorithm, Servomotor.

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Corresponding author: inunugoloma@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Photovoltaics convert light energy from the sun to electrical energy. The discovery was made in 1839 by French scientist Edmund Becquerel and was fully understood in the nineteenth century after the development of quantum theory. The US was the first country to develop the PV for commercial use in the 1950s for satellites. The PV comprises of PV cells, it is the interconnection of such that form the PV module. Its principle of operation is that; when the sun rays hit a PV cell the photons absorbed provide sufficient energy to the electrons in the covalent bonds in the cell material to break away and become free to move around the cell, hence creating and filling in the holes. The movement of the holes and electrons then generates the electricity. The PV module can either be the flat plate type or the concentrator type. The flat plate types are the most common; they are less complicated but use higher number of interconnected cells. The concentrator types are more complicated; they have lower numbers of cells but require a more complicated and expensive tracking arrangement (*Olivia 1998*).

Non-renewable energy sources most especially fossil fuels have so many serious disadvantages over renewable energy sources. The solar energy was identified as the most abundant renewable energy and more uniformly distributed around the globe than others such as the wind energy and energy from biomass. Researches have shown that the maximum solar radiation intensity is about 1.2kW/m² around the equator during clear days, an average received energy of 6-8kWh/m² per day. Nigeria lies between 4⁰N and 14⁰N of the equator and it is within the region that has at least 200 sunny days annually. Results of various studies in Nigeria show that the country is blessed with huge amount of solar energy, with a total annual solar energy received of approximately 5x10¹²kWh, daily mean radiation of 15.4 – 22.6 MJ/m² /day, mean daily sunshine is 3.5-7.0 hrs, and mean daily overcast of 1.5 – 5.5 hrs. The values are high on the average for the country as a whole but relatively higher in the Northern part. These have made solar energy an attractive renewable energy source in Nigeria, and hence the need for harvesting it using appropriate techniques as efficiently as possible (*Abdulrahim et al. 2010*).

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Researches have shown that using a tracking system increases the amount of energy received by about 30% (Robert and Isaac 2007).

METHODOLOGY

This paper was concerned with how to improve the dynamics of the PV module which is positioned by a field controlled DC servomotor arrangement in order to maximize the conversion of solar energy to electrical energy by tracking the sun rays or making the sun rays perpendicular to the surface of the module in response to the actuating actions or signals. In order to accomplish our aim three control approaches were applied to the system: The Ziegler-Nichols, pole placement and the linear quadratic regulator (Katsuhiko 2010) methods. The Ziegler-Nichols is a technique used for turning PID controllers. It can be used on both plants that their mathematical model can be obtained and complex plants that because of the nature of the system it is very difficult to obtain their model (Stephen and Craig 1991). When using the pole placement method the controller will be designed such that the poles of the closed loop system are placed at particular locations in order to have a specified damping ratio and natural frequency for improved operation of the system (Katsuhiko 2010). The linear quadratic regulator approach provides a standard way of determining the closed loop system gains by optimizing the system's performance index (Katsuhiko 2010).

Nomenclature

Symbols in this text have the following meanings unless where defined otherwise at point of usage:

Symbol	Meaning
r_a	Armature Resistance
r_f	Field Resistance
i_a	Armature Current
i_f	Field Current
PID	Proportional-Integral-Derivative
K	Voltage Constant
K_t	Torque Constant
l_a	Armature Circuit Inductance
l_f	Field Circuit Inductance
θ_0	Output/PV Position
τ_m	Developed Torque
KVL	Kirchhoff's Voltage Law
J_T	Moment of inertia of the system load referred to the motor
F_T	Coefficient of damping of the system load referred to the motor
N	Gear Ratio

Dynamic Model of the Servomotor Control PV Module

Figure 1 is an illustration of the system; where the PV module was the load to the field controlled DC servomotor. The servomotor was used for positioning the PV module in response to appropriate signal at the input. From Figure (1), the field voltage is related to the desired position of the load which is the PV module in this case. The relationship can be obtained using KVL at the input side:

$$v_f = K\theta_i \quad \dots (1)$$

It is also related to field circuit component as shown in equation (2); which can be obtained using KVL along the field loop:

$$v_f = r_f i_f + l_f \frac{di_f}{dt} \quad \dots (2)$$

Equating (1) and (2) and making the field current the subject;

$$i_f = \frac{K\theta_i}{r_f + l_f \frac{d}{dt}} \quad \dots (3)$$

The torque developed by the servomotor is given by:

$$\tau_m = K_1 i_f \quad \dots (4)$$

It is also related to the moment of inertia and coefficient of friction

$$\tau_m = J_T \frac{d^2\theta_0}{dt^2} + F_T \frac{d\theta_0}{dt} \quad \dots (5)$$

Where J_T is the ratio of the summation of the moment of inertia of the servomotor and the PV module to gear ratio N and F_T is the summation of the ratio of coefficient of damping of the servomotor and the PV module to the motor to gear ratio N. Substituting (3) into the expression obtained after equating equations and making the ratio $\frac{\theta_0}{\theta_i}$ the subject of the formula:

$$\frac{\theta_0}{\theta_i} = \frac{KK_1}{\left(r_f + l_f \frac{d}{dt}\right) \frac{d}{dt} \left(F_T + J_T \frac{d}{dt}\right)} \quad \dots (6)$$

Which after s-domain transformation and arranging becomes:

$$\frac{\theta_0(s)}{\theta_i(s)} = \frac{\left(\frac{KK_1}{J_T l_f}\right)}{\left(s^3 + \left(\frac{F_T}{J_T} + \frac{r_f}{l_f}\right)s^2 + \left(\frac{r_f F_T}{l_f J_T}\right)s\right)} \quad \dots (7)$$

Equation (8) is the transfer function of the plant; which is the PV module positioning system after substituting both the servomotor and PV module parameters, while equations (9) and (10) are the state space representation of the system.

$$\frac{\theta_0(s)}{\theta_i(s)} = \frac{53.75}{0.5s^3 + 7.5s^2 + 25s} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\dot{x} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -50 & -15 \end{bmatrix} \bar{x} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 107.5 \end{bmatrix} \bar{u} \quad \dots (9)$$

$$y = [1 \quad 0 \quad 0] \bar{x} + [0] \bar{u} \quad \dots (10)$$

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SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The controller gains were obtained using three different methods: Ziegler-Nichols shown in equation (11); using the Ziegler-Nichols approach, pole placement method shown in equation (12); and linear quadratic regulator method given in equation (13). The poles were placed at $-15+j30$, $-15-j30$ and -12 using the pole-placement method.

$$[K_d \quad K_p \quad K_i] = [0.5801 \quad 2.5450 \quad 3.3040] \quad \dots (11)$$

$$[k(1) \quad k(2) \quad k(3)] = [125.5814 \quad 13.3488 \quad 31.6] \quad \dots (12)$$

$$[k(1) \quad k(2) \quad k(3)] = [1095.4 \quad 265.0 \quad 31.6] \quad \dots (13)$$

Figures 2, 3, 4 and 5 are the Unit Step Responses of the system without controller, with controller using the Ziegler-Nichols approach, with controller designed using the Pole-Placement approach and with controller using the Linear Quadratic Regulator approach respectively. Also, from the graphs response parameters were determined as: rise time; 0.9800 seconds, peak time; 1.3600 seconds, settling time; 2.0150 seconds and overshoot; 10.3% without controller, rise time; 0.3600 seconds, peak time; 0.6950 seconds, settling time; 1.9150 seconds and overshoot; 19.8 % with controller realized using the Ziegler-Nichols method, rise time; 0.1950 seconds, peak time; 0.5000 seconds, settling time; 0.4000 seconds and overshoot; 00.0 % with controller designed using the Pole-Placement method, rise time; 0.5750 seconds, peak time; 0.7600 seconds, settling time; 1.0100 seconds and overshoot; 04.1 % with controller achieved using the Linear Quadratic Regulator method. Hence, it implies that the pole placement method has produced the best controller for the system, followed by the linear quadratic regulator method, and the Ziegler-Nichols method.

CONCLUSION

In this paper the control algorithms were successfully proposed for efficient tracking of solar radiation for a servomotor controlled photovoltaic module using the Ziegler-Nichols, pole placement and linear quadratic regulator approaches. Also, the results were successfully simulated using MATLAB 2010a (*Mathworks 2012*) which showed that all methods used have improved the system response with the Pole-Placement control method being the best for the system.

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Figure 1: An Illustration of the DC Servomotor PV Module Positioning System

Figure 2: Unit Step Response of the System without Controller

Figure 3: Unit Step Response of the System using Ziegler-Nichols Approach

Figure 4: Unit Step Response of the System using Pole-Placement Approach

Figure 5: Unit Step Response of the System using Linear Quadratic Regulator Approach